

REPOPSI

The open repository of psychological instruments in Serbian

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PSSOH (Application of Free Software and Open Hardware)

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Aleksandra Lazić, presenter

Department of psychology and Laboratory for research of individual differences,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Ljiljana B. Lazarević

Institute of psychology and Laboratory for research of individual differences,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Danka Purić

Department of psychology and Laboratory for research of individual differences,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Iris Žeželj

Department of psychology and Laboratory for research of individual differences,
University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Hello, World!

REPOPSI, osf.io/5zb8p/

Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian [Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata na srpskom jeziku] (REPOPSI)

Established and is maintained by researchers and students at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences (LIRA), University of Belgrade.

Hosted on the Open Science Framework (OSF) – a free, open-source web application of the nonprofit Center for Open Science.

We started working on REPOPSI in May 2019. The OSF project was made publicly available on March 6, 2020.

Why

REPOPSI

Majority of the standardized psychological instruments (e.g., items, scales, questionnaires, tests) were originally created in English and need to be translated/adapted to other cultural contexts.

Issues

No centralized repository of such translations/adaptations in Serbian.

Overlapping translation/adaptation efforts.

Limited opportunities to ensure the visibility of original instruments developed by local researchers.

Scriberia

Why REPOPSI

Benefits

A centralized repository of translations/adaptations in Serbian.

Makes existing translations/adaptations more easily findable and reusable.

Increases the visibility of original instruments developed by local (and regional) researchers.

What instruments are in **REPOPSI**

Holds psychological instruments (e.g., items, scales, questionnaires, tests).

Most of the instruments measure characteristics of individuals (e.g., personality, attitudes, beliefs, emotions, values, intentions) and are developed to be used in social and behavioral science research.

REPOPSI

Currently contains **140 instrument records**:

101 instruments are open-access and available in the Repository;

3 instruments are open-access but are available elsewhere online;

36 instruments are available upon request from the contact author.

How can the instruments be used?

All Repository content is under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International license.

The instruments are used free of charge for non-commercial purposes (e.g., academic research or education).

creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/

What languages are in
REPOPSI

Documents primarily instruments in Serbian and instruments translated into Serbian and/or adapted for the Serbian population.

Also documented are versions of these instruments in English as well as in other languages.

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REPOPSI Contribution Form, available upon request at lira@f.bg.ac.rs

Available in various formats
(e.g., CSV, ODS, XLSX).

Contains detailed instructions in English,
with input formats and example inputs.

<i>Instrument record</i>	<i>Input</i> <i>Please enter the information in</i> <i>this column</i>	<i>Input format</i>	<i>Example</i> <i>Please do not delete the</i> <i>information in this column</i>
Title of the instrument in English.		text Please omit the article ("The") at the beginning of the title.	Amoralism Scale Belief in Just World Scale

The completed form is sent back to LIRA.

REPOPSI Contribution Form

Divided into two parts:

Part 1

title in English and Serbian *
title abbreviation *
terms of use *
keywords in English *
languages in which it is deposited *
citation *
authors *
date of creation *
specialized tags in English
publisher
funding / contracts
abstract in English
contact person
external open-access link
additional notes in English

Part 2

instrument items *
items presentation order *
introductory sentences for respondents
instructions for respondents
response scale
instructions for administrators
scoring instructions
additional notes

* *mandatory fields*

Contributors may also submit the scoring code as a file format of their choosing (e.g., R code file, SPSS syntax file).

REPOPSI Inventory, osf.io/mxrc2/

All records are listed in the Inventory (CSV; XLSX)

Information provided in the first part of the contribution form is entered as metadata.

Show rows with cells including: <input type="text" value="children"/>		
<i>▲ Title in English.</i>	Varying form...	Varying form...
Narcissistic Personality Questionnaire for Children	Upitnik narcisti...	NPQC
Sibling Relationship Questionnaire	Upitnik za pro...	SRQ
Stereotypes Towards Roma People Scale Adapted for Children	Skala stereoti...	STRP-C

The Inventory is directly searchable by users within the OSF application via a search box.

REPOPSI's OSF project

OSF | Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian [Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata na srpskom jeziku] (REPOPSI)

osf.io/5zb8p/

Unique and persistent URL

OSFHOME

Project Navigation

Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian [Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata na srpskom jeziku] (REPOPSI)

3.3MB Public v 1 ...

Contributors: Aleksandra Lazić, Lili Lazarevic, Iris Zezelj, Danka Purić

Date created: 2019-10-04 06:42 PM | Last Updated: 2020-09-06 04:15 PM

Identifier: DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P

Category: Project

Digital Object Identifier

Click [Read More](#) to learn how to use and contribute to this Repository.

Wiki pages in Serbian and English

About

REPOPSI was launched on March 6, 2020 to provide a repository for open-access psychological measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in Serbian. REPOPSI is maintained by researchers at the [Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences \(LIRA\)](#) at the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade.

We wanted to assemble in one place all of the psychological instruments which have been translated into Serbian and/or adapted for the Serbian population, as well as all of the psychological instruments which our researchers and students have developed (either in Serbian or in other languages). REPOPSI will increase the visibility and availability of these instruments. Being a good starting point for any research project, REPOPSI will help students and researchers quickly find the instruments they need.

REPOPSI currently contains **140** records (as of August 29, 2020). More records will be added as soon as they become available, so we invite you to check back for updates.

- [About](#)
- [How to Use REPOPSI](#)
- [Contribute to REPOPSI](#)
- [Terms of Use](#)
- [Disclaimer](#)
- [Team](#)

Please click [here](#) for the version in Serbian.

REPOPSI's components

Components

Disintegration Scale - DELTA9

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

Superstition Scale - SBBS

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

Amoralism Scale - AMRL9

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

Attitudes on Academic Honesty - ATTAH

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

National Identification Scales - NIS

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

Adult Crying Inventory - ACI

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

Affective Neuroscience Personality Scales - ANPS

Lazić, Lazarevic, Zezelj & 1 more

Unique and persistent URL for each component

HEXACO Personality Inventory - HEXACO-PI

Public 1 ...

Contributors: Aleksandra Lazić, Lili Lazarevic, Iris Zezelj, Danka Purić
Date created: 2020-02-10 09:59 PM | Last Updated: 2020-07-07 02:57 PM
Category: Methods and Measures
License: Other

Files

Download View Filter i

Name	Modified
HEXACO Personality Inventory - HEXACO-PI	
OSF Storage (Germany - Frankfurt)	
hexacopir_sr_100_srp.pdf	2020-06-10 05:53 PM
hexacopir_sr_60_srp.pdf	2020-06-10 05:53 PM
hexacopir_sr_100_srp.odt	2020-05-29 01:08 AM
hexacopir_sr_60_srp.odt	2020-05-29 01:08 AM
hexacopir_100_syntax.sps	2020-02-10 10:31 PM

Each contribution documented as a separate file, in two open formats

Unique and persistent URL for each file

File naming conventions

delta9_120_eng.odt
(Version: 2)

Download Share View Revisions

Version control

- Filter
- Disintegration ...
- OSF Stora...
- delta9_1...**
- delta9_1...
- delta9_2...
- delta9_2...

Page: 1 of 5 Automatic Zoom

Title in English.	Disintegration Scale
Varying form of the title - translation.	Skala dezintegracije
Varying form of the title - abbreviation.	DELTA9
Version.	120-item
License.	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0
Original publisher.	
Local publisher.	
Funding projects, sponsoring agencies/individuals, or contractual arrangements.	
Abstract.	
Keywords.	disintegration, schizotypy, psychosis proneness, schizo-phenomena
Available languages.	eng
Contact person.	Knezevic, Goran
Contact email address.	gknezevi@f.bg.ac.rs
Citation of the original instrument.	Knezevic, G., Savic, D., Kutlesic, V., & Opačić, G. (2017). Disintegration: A Reconceptualization of Psychosis Proneness as a Personality Trait Separate from the Big Five. <i>Journal of Research in Personality</i> , 70, 187-201.
Source of the original instrument.	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2017.06.001

File preview

Customizable tags in English

Tags:

hexaco

personality structure

six factor model

"repository" AND "psychology" AND "serbian"

All

Images

News

Videos

Maps

More

Settings

Tools

About 2,380,000 results (0.68 seconds)

Displayed in search engine results

osf.io › ... ▾ Translate this page

Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian ... - OSF

Oct 4, 2019 — **Repository** of psychological instruments in **Serbian** [Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata ... measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in **Serbian**. ... sciencepersonality**psychology**REPOPSIscales**serbians**social ...

Name ^ v	Size	Version	Downloads	Modified...
✎ HEXACO Personality Inventory - HEXACO-PI				
- 🌐 OSF Storage (Germany - Frankfurt)				
📄 hexacopir_100_syntax.sps	3.3 kB	1	13	2020-02-10 1...
📄 hexacopir_sr_100_srp.odt	20.4 kB	3	25	2020-05-29 0...
📄 hex...				...)
📄 hex...				...)
📄 hex...				...)

Publicly available analytics

REPOPSI maintenance team

Aleksandra Lazić, admin
Lili Lazarević, supervisor
Danka Purić, supervisor
Iris Žeželj, supervisor
Marija Petrović, associate
Ana Ivanov, associate
Mia Medojević, associate
Jovan Ivanović, associate

The team collaborates using a private folder on Google Drive, which doubles as back-up storage.

Repository of psychological instruments in Serbian [Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata na srpskom jeziku] (REPOPSI)

Maintenance manual in Serbian
Priručnik za održavanje na srpskom

This manual was developed by [Aleksandra Lazić](#) at the [Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences](#) of the University of Belgrade.

This manual is shared under the Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International licence (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>).

Manual in Serbian for reviewing, cleaning, and depositing the contributions (available upon request).

Assessing REPOPSI using the FAIR Data Principles

F
indable

A
ccessible

I
nteroperable

R
eusable

Assessing REPOPSI using the FAIR Data Principles

F
indable

Identifier	Name
FsF-F1-01D ✓	Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.
FsF-F1-02D ✓	Data is assigned a persistent identifier.
FsF-F2-01M ✓	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
FsF-F3-01M ✓	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.
FsF-F4-01M ✓	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.

A. Devaraju et al., "FAIRSFAIR data object assessment metrics," Zenodo, Jul. 10, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934401>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the FAIR Data Principles

A_{ccessible}

Identifier	Name
FsF-A1-01M ✓	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.
FsF-A2-01M	Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.

A. Devaraju et al., "FAIRSFAR data object assessment metrics," Zenodo, Jul. 10, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934401>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the FAIR Data Principles

Interoperable

Identifier	Name
FsF-I1-01M ✘	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
FsF-I1-02M ✘	Metadata uses semantic resources.
FsF-I3-01M ✔	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.

A. Devaraju et al., "FAIRSFAR data object assessment metrics," Zenodo, Jul. 10, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934401>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the FAIR Data Principles

R_{eusable}

Identifier	Name
FsF-R1-01MD ✓	Metadata specifies the content of the data.
FsF-R1.1-01M ✓	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.
FsF-R1.2-01M ✓	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.
FsF-R1.3-01M ✓	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.
FsF-R1.3-02D ✓	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.

A. Devaraju et al., "FAIRSFAR data object assessment metrics," Zenodo, Jul. 10, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934401>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the TRUST Principles

Assessing REPOPSI using the TRUST Principles

Transparency

Being transparent about specific repository services and data holdings that are verifiable by publicly accessible evidence.

Mission statement and scope clearly stated.

Terms of use are clearly stated.

Evidence the data documentation and curation services is not entirely publicly accessible.

D. Lin *et al.*, "The TRUST Principles for digital repositories," *Scientific Data*, vol. 7, no. 1, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the TRUST Principles

Responsibility

Being responsible for ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data holdings and for the reliability and persistence of its service.

Adheres to the designated community's metadata and curation standards.

Various data services (e.g., searchable inventory; downloading and sharing files).

Provides long-term persistence and technical validation and documentation, but quality control and authenticity protection are low.

Relies on users to decide under what conditions it is appropriate to open their work and to seek approval from original authors;
Only the contact information provided in the contribution form is deposited;
When flagged by users, REPOPSI will remove instruments from public access.

D. Lin *et al.*, "The TRUST Principles for digital repositories," *Scientific Data*, vol. 7, no. 1, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the TRUST Principles

User Focus

Ensuring that the data management norms and expectations of target user communities are met.

Strives to enforce standards and norms for data practices of its target user community (i.e., social and behavioral science researchers and students).

Encourages its contributors to fully describe the instruments and its users to provide feedback on any issues with the data.

Relevant data metrics are available to users.

D. Lin *et al.*, "The TRUST Principles for digital repositories," *Scientific Data*, vol. 7, no. 1, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the TRUST Principles

Sustainability

Sustaining services and preserving data holdings for the long-term.

Plans to ensure long-term data preservation and use are still in the conceptualization phase.

While no funding is needed at this point, REPOPSI will have to sufficiently plan for risk mitigation, disaster recovery, and succession.

D. Lin *et al.*, "The TRUST Principles for digital repositories," *Scientific Data*, vol. 7, no. 1, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>.

Assessing REPOPSI using the TRUST Principles

Technology

Providing infrastructure and capabilities to support secure, persistent, and reliable services.

Relies on the OSF to provide the infrastructure necessary to support its secure, persistent, and reliable services.

The mechanisms to mitigate cyber or physical security threats have not yet been considered.

D. Lin *et al.*, "The TRUST Principles for digital repositories," *Scientific Data*, vol. 7, no. 1, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>.

REPOPSI's plans for improvement and growth

We plan to:

Make the instruments more machine-readable (CSV, XML).

Increase the transparency of the maintenance work (GitHub).

Offer the contribution form in an online survey form.

Promote REPOPSI to a wider audience.

Scriberia

Image: Scriberia for The Turing Way community, [CC-BY](#) (Changes were made)

“Research data repositories are an essential part of the infrastructure for open science. [...] They bring considerable economic, scientific, and social benefits”

OECD, “Business models for sustainable research data repositories,” OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1787/302b12bb-en>.

REPOPSI is the first open-access repository of psychological instruments in Serbian.

Open research data repositories:

streamline the research process;

are essential for large-scale collaborations;

can be applied in teaching and learning.

Thank you for your attention!

Contact: Aleksandra.Lazic@f.bg.ac.rs

